

DEPENDENCE OF ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL ON THE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF THE MEDIUM. PART I. THE GLASS SYSTEM

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The influence of the dielectric constant of the medium on the zeta potential has been studied by the endosmotic technique in the glass system. Results appear to show an over-all diminution with decreasing dielectric constant, although the variations do not appear to be smooth in all cases.

Since Helmholtz's theory of double layer was proposed for explanation of the cataphoretic mobility of colloidal particles in an electrical field or more generally for the origin of electrical potential at the phase boundary, the dielectric constant of the medium, specially in the region of the double layer, was regarded as an important influencing factor from theoretical considerations. The dielectric constant has been invoked for explaining many observations connected with the coagulation or stability of colloids (cf. Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", 1929). But a straight-forward investigation into the relationship of the dielectric constant and the zeta potential from the experimental side has not been paid so much attention as it deserves, as will be evident from the recent literature.

Present work has been undertaken with a view to assessing the role of the dielectric constant of the medium on the magnitude of the zeta potential by a straight-forward and direct experimentation. For this reason the electrokinetic potential was measured by the endosmotic method with a number of diaphragms of different materials and of different dielectric constants, prepared by mixing soluble organic liquids in water in different proportions.

Measurement of electrokinetic potential in a porous medium, made of fine particles, in contact with non-aqueous or aqueous—non-aqueous media, has recently been carried out by a few workers. The difficulty of such measurements lies in the fact that the correction for surface conductances in diaphragms is much more difficult than in capillaries made of the same material.

Coehn and Raydt (*Ann. Physik*, 1909, 30, 777) compared the electro-osmotic velocity of different liquids through glass capillaries, but their results largely differed from those of some earlier as also of some later workers like Fairbrother and Balkin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 389, 1564), Strickler and Mathews (*ibid.*, 1922, 44, 1947), Perrin (*J. chim. phys.*, 1904, 2, 607; 1905, 3, 50) and De Smet and Delfoose (*Medikal. Koaickal. Vlaam. Akad. Wetenschap. Belg. Klasse Wetenschap.*, 1942, 4, No. 10). The exact values of the electrokinetic potential in media of organic liquids of moderate dielectric constant, such as acetone, methyl alcohol,

etc., have been carefully measured recently by Rutgers *et al.* (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, **48**, 635) in glass capillaries. Verwey (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1942, **60**, 625) made some study on the electro-osmosis through diaphragms with non-aqueous liquids, but in his experiments, surface conductance appeared not to have been taken into account.

The present communication embodies the results of experiments on electro-osmosis in diaphragms made of glass. The media used were mixtures of methyl alcohol and water and ethyleneglycol and water in different proportions. Lithium chloride or sodium nitrate at a relatively high concentration was used for elimination of surface conductance in these experiments. The dielectric constant and viscosity of these mixtures were measured side by side and the endosmotic mobility correlated with the dielectric constant.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl alcohol, ethyleneglycol and lithium chloride used in these experiments were all of E. Merck's "Extra Pure" quality. The glass used for the diaphragm was obtained by pulverisation of pyrex glass into 150 to 200 mesh and sieved through standard sieves. The powdered glass used was washed with equilibrium water (sp. conductance 1.85×10^{-8} mho at 35°) several times till the conductance of the wash water showed no change on keeping in contact with the powder. Lithium chloride solution of sufficient concentration was also prepared with the same water. All experiments were performed at a temperature of $35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Endosmotic experiments were carried out with the same apparatus as designed by Briggs *et al.* (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, **22**, 256) and recommended by Mukherjee and Basu (*this Journal*, 1927, **4**, 461) and reported in details by Ghosh and Ray (*ibid.*, 1939, **16**, 634). Temperature in all measurements (endosmosis, viscosity, or dielectric constant) was maintained at $35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ by an electrically controlled thermostat.

Measurement of dielectric constant was carried out by the heterodyne beat method. The apparatus with a piezo-electric quartz crystal (3 m.c.) oscillator was locally designed and made to order by a local firm. The apparatus was first calibrated and tested for its performance by checking the dielectric constants of a large number of known and standard liquids dielectric constants of which were accurately known. The accuracy of measurements was found to be within 1%.

The zeta potential was calculated from the endosmotic mobility of the bubble in cm/sec./unit potential gradient by the help of the equation

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta\kappa v}{Di} \times (300)^2 \text{ volts}$$

where, η = viscosity coeff., v = vol. of liquid flowing per sec., κ = sp. conductivity, D = dielectric constant and i = current in amp. Results are recorded in the following tables

TABLE I

Glass diaphragm in alcohol-water mixture.

Temp. = 35°. LiCl = 0.14 N.

% EtOH by vol.	D.	η (poise).	ζ (mv.).	% MeOH by vol.	D.	η (poise).	ζ (mv.).
0	76.00	0.00721	54.13	0	76.00	0.00721	54.13
10	74.30	0.00955	48.72	10	74.30	0.00859	57.18
20	68.40	0.01285	44.18	20	69.21	0.00956	54.83
30	60.78	0.01426	41.59	30	64.98	0.01078	49.17
40	56.50	0.01568	52.14	40	60.74	0.01166	48.88
50	50.58	0.01607	55.51	50	58.20	0.01158	36.39
60	44.65	0.01642	68.96	60	55.65	0.01160	38.90
70	38.72	0.01591	63.93	70	48.03	0.01015	30.28
100	27.27	0.01111	58.80				

TABLE II

Glass diaphragm in ethyleneglycol-water mixture.

Temp. = 35°. LiCl = 0.14 N.

% Eth. glyc. by vol.	D.	η (poise).	ζ (mv.).	% Eth. glyc. by vol.	D.	η (poise).	ζ (mv.).
0	76.00	0.00721	54.13	50	59.89	0.02420	48.55
10	74.30	0.00929	46.34	60	55.65	0.03149	45.50
20	71.76	0.01180	54.21	70	51.00	0.04201	40.74
30	68.36	0.01508	49.55	80	49.73	0.05625	28.15
40	66.25	0.01920	44.28	90	44.22	0.07577	29.00

TABLE III

*AgI ppt. diaphragm in EtOH-H₂O.*Temp. = 35°. NaNO₃ = 0.14 N.

% EtOH.	D.	η (poise).	ζ (mv.).	% EtOH.	D.	η (poise).	ζ (mv.).
0	76.00	0.00721	59.70	50	50.58	0.01607	91.11
10	74.30	0.00955	86.14	60	44.65	0.01642	89.32
20	68.40	0.01285	91.52	70	38.72	0.01591	89.16
30	60.78	0.01426	117.10	80	34.47	0.01541	89.45
40	56.50	0.01568	122.10	90	30.00	0.01331	99.23

DISCUSSION

Results indicate quite a marked effect of the dielectric constant of the medium on the ζ -potential. In the case of the glass diaphragm in ethyl alcohol-water

mixture, the ζ -potential at first diminishes with diminution of D , the dielectric constant, but beyond 40% of alcohol there has been a steady increase till at 70% it is observed to show some diminution at higher concentrations. The value in pure alcohol, however, comes up to a value almost equal to that in water (0% alcohol). In the case of methyl alcohol, however, there was a steady decrease in the value of the ζ -potential almost from the beginning up to 70% alcohol beyond which it was not possible to pursue further, as the results obtained were not found to be reproducible with direct and reverse currents. Such data have been rejected and only those which were found reproducible, both in the direct and reverse currents as well as by repetitions of the experiments at least thrice (and in some cases at least five times), have been shown in the table. The cause of the appearance of such irreproducibility could not be properly understood. It might be due to some disturbing effect appearing with increase in the concentration of methyl alcohol. With ethyl alcohol, the values of ζ -potential began to increase again when the dielectric constant diminished from 60.78 to 56.50 (with alcohol conc. 40% to 50%), but with methyl alcohol no such thing was observed. A continuous decrease persisted all through till the value of zeta reached as low a value as 30.28. These data are more or less in agreement with some of Rutger's observations, which were made in some other connections.

With ethyleneglycol, there has been a similar behaviour as in methyl alcohol in the fact that the observations could not be pursued beyond 90% concentration of glycol. At 90% a slight irreversibility appears, but it is extremely small and the data presented here are the outcome of five to ten repetitions. Only in the case of 40% glycol, there has been some anomaly which has also been confirmed by repetition and checking up of the data for 30% and 50% (one preceding the anomalous datum and the other succeeding it but since the sequence was observed to be the same in every case) the data have been presented from their mean values.

Owing to the difference in behaviour observed in the case of glass diaphragms, the whole set of experiments were repeated in the case of silver iodide diaphragm with media of varying dielectric constants. Only the data for ethyl alcohol and water mixture have been presented in Table III. Data for methyl alcohol or glycol and water are very much similar and have not been presented here for economy of space. Results show an initial increase but later on, a slight decrease has also been noticed to occur, followed again by further increase. Behaviours with methyl alcohol and glycol are also similar.

From the behaviour of glass diaphragms in different media, it was suspected that the actual behaviour might be due to the ionic activity. According to Debye-Hückel's law, the activity coefficient is given by

$$\log f = -AZ_+Z_- \sqrt{\mu} + C\mu$$

where A is a constant depending on the dielectric constant and temperature, C , the salting out constant and μ , the ionic strength. In the present experiments where μ is kept constant by using LiCl or NaNO_3 of the same concentration, as in the

case of the glass diaphragm with methyl alcohol and ethyleneglycol, the same dielectric constant yields the same value of zeta, specially at lower concentrations of the non-electrolytes. At higher non-electrolyte concentrations, however, a slight divergence begins to appear. It appears that at lower percentages of the non-aqueous liquids, the constant A is the decisive factor, but at higher concentrations, the salting out constant C comes into prominence. Most probably owing to this reason the data at higher alcohol concentrations show erratic behaviour so far as their reversibility is concerned.

Therefore it appears that the activity coefficient of ions, as normally expected, would exert influence on the value of ζ -potential. Variation of the dielectric constant influences the value of A in the Debye-Hückel expression for the activity coefficient, and this affects the values of zeta. At higher percentages of the non-electrolyte, the value of C (the salting out constant) is probably also influenced owing to the change in the nature of the medium, and the behaviours at higher concentrations of alcohol do not tally with those at lower concentrations.

The point is interesting and deserves intensive investigation. Further work is being done with different systems and more non-aqueous media. Results will be published in future communications.

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